

Educational Studies Association of Ireland - 2025 Conference
Abstract - Early Career Researcher

Class dismissed? How Socio-Economic Contexts Shape Young People's Understanding and Experiences of (Cyber)Bullying Across Physical and Digital Worlds

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This presentation highlights the role of socio-economic and cultural contexts in shaping (cyber)bullying behaviours, as well as the diverse digital spaces that young people inhabit in informing and influencing their identities and social interactions.

As schools are increasingly asked to address online safety, a broader understanding of how (cyber)bullying stretches across physical and digital spaces is needed. By exploring how these intersecting spaces impact social dynamics within schools, this study sheds light on how (cyber)bullying behaviours emerge, evolve, and are understood across different socio-economic and cultural contexts.

Based on an ethnographic study in two schools situated in different socio-economic contexts in Ireland, this presentation offers insights into how young people's experiences and understandings of (cyber)bullying are embedded within their physical and digital social environments. The complex interplay between the socio-economic contexts, along with the different digital spaces and norms create distinct landscapes where diverse forms of (cyber)bullying can take root. In this way, young people's identities and social positions are constructed and negotiated across unique and specific environments, where certain norms and behaviours are reinforced while others are challenged.

This research offers a sociological lens to view young people not merely in static roles of "victim," "perpetrator," or "bystander" but as social actors implicated in complex networks of interaction. This approach offers nuanced insights into how social structures, cultural values, and power dynamics perpetuate (cyber)bullying, providing a deeper understanding of the broader social forces that enable it to expand - especially within a society increasingly shaped by digital transformations. This allows for a significant potential in de-constructing and transforming the structural injustices that are at the heart of (cyber)bullying.

The presentation will also critically discuss positionality in conducting an ethnographic study as a young foreign researcher in Irish schools situated in different socio-economic contexts.

Implications for practice highlights the need for anti-bullying strategies that are sensitive to the specific socio-economic, cultural and digital contexts that shape a multitude of diverse childhoods, thereby addressing the specific factors that shape (cyber)bullying behaviours in both physical and digital spaces. This is particularly important as current anti-bullying interventions often struggle to tackle the multifold co-existence of (cyber)bullying in between physical and digital spaces (Bork-Hüffer, Mahlke, and Kaufmann 2021) - and how this interconnection shapes young people's sense of belonging and othering.